

The Terracotta temple of Antpur: An Attempt to Study the Importance of Heritage Management

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Abstract

Cultural Resource Management is gradually gaining importance in the present world. The act of preserving the cultural heritage of any community seems to be one of the duties which rests on the shoulders of both the institutions like state and the citizens. The cultural history of any nation can be presented to the future generation through their proper preservation, documentation and spreading awareness. In this context, West Bengal is one of the richest states having great traditions of cultural history, exhibiting a vast variety of historical cultural heritage. Antpur is a small village of West Bengal having historical significance. The most famous temple in Antpur is that of Radha Govinda jiu with exquisite Terracotta carvings depicting mythical stories. This particular place houses several terracotta temples through a temple complex. These terracotta temples not only show a great artistic sign of work, but also store a rich cultural heritage within its structure. The present study is the result of a fieldwork conducted at this place with an aim to study the architectural value of the structures and at the same time find out the social importance of these historical monuments in local as well as broader scenario. It also highlights the functioning of the heritage management schemes in the site.

Key Words: CRM, Architecture, Terracotta, Antpur

Introduction

Antpur is a village in the Jangipara community development block of the Shirampur subdivision in the Hooghly district in the Indian state of West Bengal. It is around 20 km from Tarakeswar, the famous temple town and railhead for the SheoraphuliTarakeswar section.

The most famous temple in Antpur is that of RadhaGovindajiu with exquisite Terracotta carvings depicting stories from all the 18 Purana. This 100-foot-high temple was constructed by Kishna Ram Mitra, the Diwan of Bardhaman Raj in 1786. It's Chandni Mandap and Dol Mancha has beautifully crafted wood carvings and Terracotta.

Cultural resource management is a process to understand the past culture. It is a process which studies ancient monuments, ancient buildings and Temple etc. RadhaGovinda Jiu temple is one of the oldest temples in this region. This temple is socially as well as location wise quite significant, so this work is very important to understand the social importance and to know about the past culture.

Reviewing the Literature Source

Since the time immortal Indian culture represents a glorious legacy of cultural heritage. Various architectures, memorials, buildings comprise the tangible heritages, whereas the oral tradition of folk lore, songs, dance form etc create the intangible domain. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) defines 'Heritage' as "our legacy from the past, what we live with today, and what we pass on to the future generations" whereas, 'Cultural Heritage' has been described as, "the irreplaceable sources of life and inspiration that include monuments such as architectural works of monumental sculpture and painting, elements of structures of an archaeological nature, inscriptions, cave dwelling and combinations of features; groups of buildings, groups of separate or connected buildings; and sites including archaeological sites having outstanding historical, aesthetic, ethnological or anthropological value"(UNESCO, 1971).

On the other hand, 'Heritage Management and Conservation' means a continuous effort, those comprise of perfect maintenance and preservation of heritage elements from being demolished or reservation without proper management, control, and appropriate methods. (Gantait et al, 2018). The objectives of heritage management would be best achieved when the roles of stakeholders are properly recognized and carried out. (Gupta and Prathama). There are several agencies who act as

stakeholder like the Government body, different autonomous local self-government body, Academic institutions, NGOs and the common people. The government plays a key role in ensuring adequate funding and staffing for management, and other autonomous bodies take responsibility to take initiatives regarding the preservation of the heritages in terms of material conservation as well as preservation of intangible cultural importance.

Destruction in due course of time is one of the natural causes of disappearance from the scenario, but several man-made causes are there like the infrastructural development, extension of urban setting etc. the fact is very much clear that in most of the cases least awareness about the historical as well as cultural importance of the monuments, architectures are the cause of gradual destruction (Carlos, 2011).

The present work mainly focuses on this theoretical background and it has tried to document the architectural importance as well as the cultural significance of a temple complex having great historical mark in the mediaeval history of the Bengal.

Aims and objectives of the study

The Present study concentrates on the following objectives:

To understand the structure and architecture of temple of the Lord Radha Govinda Jiu.

1. To explore the historical genesis of the cult of Lord Radha Gobinda Jiu at the studied area.
2. The socio-economic significance of the temple in the locality.
3. Try to study the heritage management at the study area.

Methodological aspect of the Present Study

Primarily the present study follows a qualitative approach of study. The data relevant for the fulfilment of the objectives of the study have been incorporated from two data sources. Different secondary resources like the Hooghly district gazetteer, other historical documents showing the

historical importance of the place as well as other information regarding the study area were also taken into account.

The fieldwork was carried out to gather primary first-hand data from various persons including the priests, trustee members, local people and other informants having valuable data about the temple complex of the studied area. Basically, unstructured interview is taken for this present study. The informants were interviewed to explore the historical importance of the place as well as the present scenario. The structure of the temples was carefully studied through using detailed observation and drawing the layout of the temple and the surrounding area. Here photographs of the site help a lot during the analysis of the architectural significance of the temples. Cases were taken from the stake holders including the priests, trustee members for getting in-depth about different aspects of the studied site, the symbolism behind the architecture of the temples, the ritualistic part of the worship of the Lord Govinda Jiu.

Antpur: The Study Area

The present study area is a small town situated in the district of Hooghly. The Hooghly itself is a place of historical importance. It is one of the places that was colonized by three different European powers between 18th Century and middle of the 19th Century. Chandannagar (earlier known as Farash Danga) was a French Colony whereas the Shreerampore was colonized by the Dutches. Rest of the part was under the control of the British. Before the European colonization in the district, the Islamic rulers of Bengal had a strong hold in the district. The district as mentioned earlier shows great heritage tradition of various religious sects with local influence. The presence of Tarakeswar temple, Hangseswari Tmple, Bandel Church, Pandua Bari Masjid etc. exhibit the co-existence of different religious beliefs at a single place.

Antpur is a village in the Jangipara community development block of the Serampore subdivision in the Hooghly district in West Bengal. It is around 20 km from Tarakeswar, the famous temple town and railhead for the Sheoraphuli-Tarakeswar station.

The village was the birthplace of Baburam Ghosh (later Swami Premananda). It was at Antpur where Swami Vivekananda and eight other disciples of Sri Ramakrishna took their vow of 'sannyasa' on 24 December 1886. The Ramakrishna-Premananda Ashram of Antpur has built a temple on the birthplace of Swami Pramananda.

There are interesting stories about the origin of the name Antpur. According to some Antpur was named after the zamindar Atar Khan while other believe the Antpur is a combination of eight villages of BhuriShreshtha kingdom and hence the name Antpur.

Radha-Govinda Jiu temple: History and Architecture

The *Radha-Govinda Jiu* temple is placed near the pitched road. The main Antpur temple is surrounded by *Dol-mancha* temple, *Ras-mancha* temple, *Jaleswar* temple, *Fuleswar* temple, *Gangadhar* temple and *Baneswar* temple. There is a big pond at the south side of the main temple. On the northern side the *Ramkrishna Math* is located and a *Durga-Mancha* is also present.

This temple is one of the oldest temples in Bengal. It is one of the heritage sites of Bengal. This Temple Gate remains open from 11am to 6 pm daily for the people. No entry ticket is required and this temple is open for all to make prayer.

The temple is an example of great artistic work of terracotta carvings depicting stories from all the Eighteen *Puranas*. This 100 feet high temple having a sloped roof of Eight Sides (*Aat-Chala*). The temple has total area approximately 9000 square meter. The area that the main temple cover is approximately 250 square metre. The courtyard area of the temple covered is 4800 square meter. It costs near about 1 lakhs of the then money. The temple has a triple arched entrance and the entire front face is covered with the finest terracotta plaques. The temple was constructed by Krishna Ram Mitra, the Diwan of Bardhaman Raj in 1786 (1708 Shakabda). Its *Chandi-Mandap* and *Dol-Mancha* have beautifully crafted wood carvings and terracotta tiles. Muslim rule was ebbing out and the Europeans were making forays into the country. It is said that Krishna Ram Mitra built the temple to enthuse the Hindus. The terracotta panels reflect this transition. Apart from traditional panels showing images of Gods & Goddesses and scenes from *Ramayana* &

Krishnaleela, it also houses a vast number of panels showing European lifestyles. European soldiers with bayonet mounted guns and hunting scenes with dogs are abundant on the walls of the temple. The Panels display the stories of Radha and Krishna predominantly, at the same time presence of the goddess Durga and other Tantric gods and goddesses are also noticed. Presently, there are 5 entrances in the temple. Three of them are present on the front side of the temple and the remaining two are present on the right and left side of the temple separately. There are a total number of 3 rooms present in the temple. There are 2 *dalans* are present in the main temple. Among the 3 rooms the central room is the place for worship of the Lord *Radha-Govinda Jiu*. In this temple 3 windows are visible in each room. In this temple after the entrances there are 3 gates. In the inner most part where the two separate rooms are linked with the main big room 2 doors are present in each of them.

Besides the main temple of *Radha-Govinda Jiu* there are the temples of Lord Shiva having different names like *Gangadhara, Fuleswara, Rameswara, Jaleswara* and *Baneswara*.

Radha-Govinda Jiu temple: Changing Scenario

Now the condition of the temple is not very well. The wall paintings of the temple are almost extinct. The designs of the outer walls of the temple have almost disappeared. There is a plan to make the infrastructure beautiful and sustainable inside the temple. Marble has been placed inside the temple. Two priests worship twice a day in the morning and afternoon. Sometimes college students and foreigners came to visit and know something about the temple. The electrical system of the temple is being improved. The arrangement is being taken to maintain the wall design of the temple.

Continuous renovation works are being undertaken by the authority. Though the main temple 'Sri Sri Radha-Govinda-Jiu Mandir' does not get any huge damage in recent years but the excellent Terracotta works have been destructed gradually. Beside this, some temples are now in great danger. Other temples are plastered by the cement for which the Terracotta work have been vanished. The architecture near *Durga-Mancha* becomes totally destroyed.

Significance of Heritage Management of the Temple

The Temple exhibits an excellent art work of Traditional Bengal Terracotta plaques. As it has been observed from the terracotta panels fixed on the wall of the temple it appears that the temple not only shows the traditional Hinduistic art form rather the presence of different plates of modern images. The historical transformation of the then Bengal can be viewed in the terracotta plates. Local history of the place can also be depicted from the study of the temple, its ritualistic part and as during the interview of the priests they spoke about the changes in the worship patterns at the temple. According to them, though the main temple has somewhat importance in the present time but the other temples like the Shiva Temples are not worshipped now-a-days. The structural condition of these temples are also decaying day by day. So, there should be an awareness among the local people about the historical as well as architectural significance of the temple complex. The local Government as well as the intellectuals also have a lot of duties for preserving the heritage. The reservation of these temples will not only preserve the history of the state but also proper management and promotion of the place will enrich the tourist destinations of Bengal itself.

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